

The electrical circuit of the cell

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ABSTRACT: The role of ATP is to turn Gerald Pollack's "EZ water" into an electrical circuit. ATP "extends" the circuit, by moving the cathode, H^+ , away from the anode, $H_3O_2^-$. It does this because it is able to adsorb 4 protons when complexed to the p-loop motif, the complex has "lock in key fit" for 4 protons. The role of K^+ is to force or nudge these protons away from the $(H_3O_2^-)_n$ "surface phase". ATP and K^+ turns the EZ into a "circuit", the electrical circuit of the cell.

Introduction

The electrical circuitry of the cell is formed from the dominant parts of the cell, the primary intracellular cation K^+ , its conjugate anion phosphate, and, Gerald Pollack's discovery, the surface phase of water, $(H_3O_2^-)_n/(H_3O^+)_n$.

The "surface phase" of water

The "surface phase" of water is seen in microscopes, and it looks like ice. The first assumption would be that it was just normal ice. But, ice is less dense than water. Since this surface phase forms as water pressure pushes water at surfaces against the surfaces, forcing it into a solid phase, it should be expected to be denser than water. How could water form a solid phase that is denser than water? It does this by simply compressing ice.

Ice is made up of a stack of hexagonal lattice sheets, with hydrogen atoms separating the sheets. It can be compressed, by "squeezing" the hydrogen atoms out, or, more specifically, the proton of those atoms, leaving the electron, and then shifting adjacent sheets one atom relative one another, so that the oxygens in each sheet still contact hydrogens in the adjacent sheet.

This "compression", a result of water pressure, that ultimately comes from gravity, gives the "surface phase" the unique property that it is charge polarized. The solid part, the "ice", is not $(\text{H}_4\text{O}_2)_n$ like ice, but, $(\text{H}_3\text{O}_2^-)_n$ (stoichiometry of each hexagon in ice is H_4O_2 , same as H_2O except each hexagon is 2 H_2O .) The H^+ that was "squeezed out", combines with water next to the "ice" to form a layer of liquid $(\text{H}_3\text{O}^+)_n$ on top of it, attracted to and pressed against the "ice" because of charge.

Fig. 3.4 Microspherule-exclusion zone (EZ) next to a gel surface. The zone grows with time

Fig. 12.5 The effect of pressure on ice. The pressure squeezes out protons, which converts the ice to EZ water.

An electrical circuit from water, ATP, and K⁺

If you squeeze a liquid its phase changes into a solid, if you squeeze a gas it becomes a liquid. At surfaces, water is squeezed by the rest of the bulk water, that is itself squeezed by gravity. So you'd expect a denser-than-water solid at surfaces water contacts. And it is there. It has the unusual property that it is charge polarized. This makes it a battery. This battery can be turned into a battery + electric circuit, and the cell does that with ATP and K⁺.

The anode and cathode reaction of the cell, are analogous to those in an acid-base battery. The cell is, in fact, an acid-base battery. The anode reaction is the oxygen evolution reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$, and the cathode reaction is the oxygen reduction reaction $4 \text{H}^+ + 4 \text{e}^- + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Like often used in acid-base batteries, the cell forms an alkaline compartment using K⁺. Unlike an acid-base battery that would add a potassium hydroxide salt, the hydroxide ions are already in the cell, within the "surface water" that exists at all protein surfaces. The K⁺ bonds to the (H₃O²⁻)_n, replacing H⁺ that was already there.

The acidic compartment is formed with ATP. More specifically, using ATP when it is bound to its protein binding site, and the triphosphate tail is complexed into the p-loop motif region. The p-loop/ATP complex, behaves as a base, and adsorbs the H⁺ that was removed from the "surface phase". It does this using the combined negative charge of the (deprotonated) hydroxyl groups on the phosphates, and, the negative charge of the hydrogen bond acceptor at the p-loop. The hydroxyl groups on the phosphates is able to serve as the hydrogen bond donor because the complex itself acts as a stronger base than ATP.

The cell discharges the acid-base battery (that exists in and around every protein) by ATP hydrolysis. ADP has lower affinity for the protein binding site, and detaches, the p-loop/ATP complex that served as the base that adsorbed the H⁺ no longer exists, and the H⁺ is released. At the alkaline compartment, the (H₃O²⁻)_n phase collapses, for different reasons. It releases hydroxide ions, and these undergo the oxygen evolution reaction that releases electrons. The cell then recharges, by regenerating the ATP.